

Synthesis, characterization and DNA studies of transition metal(II) complexes of Schiff base derived from *p*-aminoacetanilide and salicylaldehyde

N. Raman*, K. Rajasekaran and A. Sakthivel

Department of Chemistry, VHNSN College, Virudhunagar-626 001, Tamilnadu, India
E-mail : drn_raman@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 28 June 2006, revised 23 November 2006, accepted 24 November 2006

Abstract : A new tridentate Schiff base ligand (HL) was prepared by the condensation of salicylaldehyde and *p*-aminoacetanilide and characterized by microanalytical data, IR, UV-Vis, ¹H NMR and mass spectra. Complexes with Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} were synthesized and characterized by spectral and analytical techniques. The data show that the complexes have composition ML₂ where M = Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}. The Schiff base acts as a tridentate mono basic donor, coordinating through the deprotonated phenolic oxygen, carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen atoms. The UV-Vis spectral data suggest that the complexes have distorted octahedral geometry. Their low electrical conductance values reveal that these chelates are non-electrolytes. Their magnetic susceptibility values provide evidence for the monomeric nature. The electrochemical experiments neatly demonstrate that the present ligand system can stabilize the higher oxidation states of metal ions. The nuclease activity of the above metal complexes shows that the complexes cleave DNA through redox chemistry. In the presence of H₂O₂, all the complexes are capable of cleaving Lambda DNA.

Keywords : Schiff base, transition metals, DNA.

The interaction of transition metal complexes with DNA is a significant area of research which has attracted much attention of both inorganic and biochemists, because biochemical studies have shown that they are related to the development of new DNA reagents for biotechnology and medicine^{1,2}. Schiff base ligands and their transition metal complexes have been extensively studied over past few decades. Of the various classes of Schiff bases which can be prepared by condensation of different types of amines and carbonyl compounds such as salicylaldehydes, potential O, N donors derived from salicylaldehydes and primary amines, are very popular due to diverse chelating ability³. Copper(II) salicylaldehyde complexes play important roles in both synthetic and structural research because of their preparative accessibility and structural diversity⁴. In addition to the varied magnetic property and catalytic activity, the metal-Schiff base complexes can also serve as efficient models for the metal containing sites in metallo-proteins and -enzymes^{5,6}.

The present investigation deals with the synthesis, characterization and nuclease activity of new Schiff base complexes derived from salicylaldehyde and *p*-aminoacetanilide.

Results and discussion

The analytical data for the ligand and complexes

together with some physical properties are summarized in Table 1. The analytical data of the complexes correspond well with the general formula [ML₂] where M = Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} and HL = C₁₅H₁₄N₂O₂. The molar conductance values of the complexes in DMSO lie in the range 1.9 to 3.6 mho cm² mol⁻¹ which are quite lower than values expected for a 1 : 1 electrolyte and reveal their non-electrolytic nature⁷.

The FAB mass spectra of the ligand and its copper complex were recorded and compared for their stoichiometry compositions. The molecular ion peak for the ligand is observed at 254 *m/z* ratio which is also supported by the "Nitrogen Rule", since the compound possesses two nitrogen atoms. The prominent peak found at 77 *m/z* is due to the phenyl group. The molecular ion peak for the copper complex was observed at *m/z* = 567, which confirms the stoichiometry of metal chelates as ML₂ type.

The IR spectra provide valuable information regarding coordination site of the ligand attached to the metal ion. Selected bands of diagnostic importance of the free ligand and its complexes are given in Table 2. From the table, it is evident that the ligand is tridentate, bonded to metal ion through azomethine nitrogen, phenolic oxygen atom of salicylaldehyde moiety and amide oxygen of *p*-aminoacetanilide moiety⁸⁻¹⁴.

Table 1. Physical characterization, analytical, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility data of the ligand and the complexes

Compd./ Complex	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Formula weight	Molar conductance Λ_m ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
			M	C	H	N			
$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$	Yellow	162	-	69.75 (70.86)	5.43 (5.57)	11.59 (11.02)	254	-	-
CuL_2	Black	283	11.89 (11.20)	63.31 (63.49)	4.67 (4.58)	8.89 (9.87)	567	3.2	1.95
CoL_2	Light brown	295	8.87 (10.44)	64.25 (63.95)	4.27 (4.61)	7.59 (9.94)	563	2.6	3.05
NiL_2	Pale green	265	10.72 (10.46)	63.82 (63.97)	4.73 (4.62)	10.25 (9.95)	562	3.6	4.10
ZnL_2	White	270	11.81 (11.48)	62.92 (63.22)	4.50 (4.56)	10.35 (9.83)	569	1.9	-

The ^1H NMR spectra of the Schiff base and its zinc complex were recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ at room temperature. The ligand shows the following signals : phenyl multiplet at δ 7–7.5, $-\text{CO}-\text{CH}_3$ at δ 2.1, $-\text{N}=\text{CH}-$ at δ 7.9, $-\text{OH}$ at δ 12.5 and PhNH at δ 8.5. The absence of peak at δ 12.5 in the zinc complex suggests that the phenolic proton is lost upon coordination. There is no appreciable change in all other signals in this complex. Thus, ^1H NMR study reinforces the conclusions drawn from the IR spectra.

Table 2. IR spectral data of the synthesized compounds

Compd.	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (cm^{-1})	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ (cm^{-1})	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ (cm^{-1})	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ (cm^{-1})	$\nu(-\text{OH})$ (cm^{-1})
[HL]	1617	1675	-	-	3100–3000
$[\text{CuL}_2]$	1595	1654	530	450	-
$[\text{CoL}_2]$	1590	1659	535	443	-
$[\text{NiL}_2]$	1587	1650	537	447	-
$[\text{ZnL}_2]$	1596	1652	540	440	-

The magnetic moment of the complexes at room temperature is consistent with an octahedral geometry around the central metal ion and monomeric nature of the complexes. Thermal analysis of the complexes at 170 °C indicates that there is no water molecules present in the complexes.

The electronic absorption spectra of the ligand and its complexes were recorded at 300 K in DMSO. The solvent, absorption region, assignment of the absorption bands and the proposed geometry of the complexes are given in Table 3. This table shows that all the complexes are having octahedral geometry around the metal ions^{15–17}.

The X-band ESR spectrum of polycrystalline copper complex in DMSO recorded at 300 and 77 K are shown in Figs. 1(a) and 1(b).

The spectrum of the complex at 300 K shows one intense absorption band in the high field region and is isotropic due to tumbling motion of the molecules. The magnetic moment (1.94 B.M.) calculated from the equation $\mu_{\text{eff}} = g[s(s + 1)]^{1/2}$ using the experimental g_{iso} values (2.26) agree very well with the measured magnetic susceptibility range of 1.92–2.02 B.M. indicating that the solid structure is retained in DMSO solution. The ESR spectrum of the copper complex at 77 K indicates a poorly resolved nitrogen super hyperfine structure in the perpendicular region due to the interaction of the Cu^{II} odd electron with nitrogen atoms. The magnetic susceptibility value reveals that the copper complex has a

Table 3. Electronic absorption spectra of the synthesized compounds in DMSO solution

Compd./ Complex	Absorption (cm^{-1})	Assignment	Solvent	Geometry
[HL]	30674	INCT	DMSO	-
$[\text{CuL}_2]$	13812	$^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2A_{2g}$	DMSO	Distorted octahedral
	23255	$^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$		
$[\text{CoL}_2]$	30395	INCT	DMSO	
	40983	INCT		
	14858	$^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$		Octahedral
	16978	$^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4A_{2g}(F)$		
$[\text{NiL}_2]$	13888	$^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}(F)$	DMSO	Octahedral
	15220	$^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(F)$		
	25380	$^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(P)$		

Fig. 1. The X band ESR spectrum of the copper complex in DMSO solution at 300 K (a) and 77 K (b).

magnetic moment, 1.95 B.M., corresponding to the one unpaired electron, indicating that the complex is mono-nuclear. This fact was also evident from the absence of a half field signal, observed in the spectrum at 1600 G due to the $m_s = \pm 2$ transitions, ruling out any Cu-Cu interaction^{18,19}.

The g -tensor value of the copper complex can be used to derive the ground state. In octahedral complexes, the unpaired electron may lie in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ or d_{z^2} orbital. The spin Hamiltonian parameters for the copper complex are calculated from the spectra. The observed order ($A_{\parallel} = 150$, $A_{\perp} = 60$; g -tensor values are $g_{\parallel} (2.36) > g_{\perp} (2.08) > g_e (2.00)$) suggest that this complex has distorted octahedral geometry with unpaired electron lying in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital.

The ESR parameters of the complex coincide well with related systems which suggest that the complexes have octahedral geometry and the systems are axially symmetric²¹. In the axial spectra, the g -values are related with exchange interaction coupling constant (G) by the expression,

$$G = g_{\parallel} - 2/g_{\perp} - 2$$

According to Hathaway²⁰, if the G value is larger than four, the exchange interaction is negligible because the local tetragonal axes are aligned parallel or slightly misaligned. If its value is less than four, the exchange interaction is considerable and the local tetragonal axes are misaligned. For the present copper complex, it is 4.5

which suggests that the local tetragonal axes are aligned parallel or slightly misaligned and consistent with a $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state.

Further, it is reported that g_{\parallel} is 2.4 for copper-oxygen bonds, 2.3 for copper-nitrogen bonds. For mixed copper-nitrogen and copper-oxygen bond system, there is a small variation in the point symmetry from octahedral geometry. For the copper complex $g_{\parallel} = 2.36$ which is in between 2.3–2.4. It shows that it is having mixed copper-nitrogen and copper-oxygen bonds in these chelates²².

Based on the above spectral data, the following structure has been proposed for the complexes (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Structure of the metal complexes.
M = Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}

The cyclic voltammogram of Cu^{II} complex (0.01 M) in DMSO solution in the absence of molecular oxygen at room temperature in 1.0 to -1.0 V potential range at scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹ is shown in the Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of the copper complex in (0.1 M TBAP) DMSO solution. Scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹.

The anodic peak at $E_{pa} = 0.42$ V versus Ag/AgCl and the associated cathodic peak at $E_{pc} = 0.36$ V correspond to the copper(II)/(III) couple. Based on the literature method^{23,24}, the number of electrons transferred during each electrochemical oxidation was computed and found to be equal to one. Further, there is an irreversible reduction at $E_{pc} = -0.47$ V, corresponding to the formation of unstable copper(I) species. The irreversible nature is due to chemical change occurs with the electron transfer.

It may be due to the structural reorganization in coordination sphere.

CV, UV-Vis and ESR data for the copper complex indicate that the filled π orbital of the ligand interacts significantly with the e_g orbitals of the copper(II). The relative difficulty of reducing the copper(III) state to copper(II) is consistent with a high electron density on the metal donated by the ligand through both its σ - and π -electron systems.

DNA cleavage was controlled by relaxation of the supercoiled circular form of Lambda form into the nicked linear form. When Lambda DNA is run on horizontal gel using electrophoresis, the fastest migration will be observed for the supercoiled form. If both strands are cleaved, a linear form will be generated that migrates in between.

In the present study, the gel electrophoretic separation of Lambda DNA, induced by the synthesized Schiff base complexes in the presence of H_2O_2 is shown in the Fig. 4. The gel electrophoresis experiment demonstrates that Schiff base complexes and H_2O_2 are required to cleave Lambda DNA. It is found that all the complexes are capable of cleaving Lambda DNA only in the presence of H_2O_2 .

Lane 1 2 3 4 5

Fig. 4. Electrophoretic separations of Lambda DNA induced by Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes.

- Lane-1 : DNA + Tris + NaCl + Cu^{II} complex
- Lane-2 : DNA + Tris + NaCl + Ni^{II} complex
- Lane-3 : DNA + Tris + NaCl + Co^{II} complex
- Lane-4 : DNA + Tris + NaCl + Zn^{II} complex
- Lane-5 : DNA + Tris + NaCl

From the observed results and the above figure, we conclude that the copper, nickel and cobalt complexes (Lane 1, 2 and 3) were completely degraded. This shows that a slight increase in concentration over the optimal value (i.e. the value at which 100% cleavage efficiency was observed) led to extensive degradations, resulting in

disappearance of bands on agarose gel. The single strand cleavage of DNA can be observed in the gel diagram for zinc complex (Lane 4).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. For the cyclic voltammetric experiments, tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) used as supporting electrolyte, was purchased from Sigma. Anhydrous grade ethanol and DMSO were purified according to standard procedures. Micro analytical data and 1H NMR spectra of the compounds were recorded at the Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Center, Central Drug Research Institute (RSIC, CDRI), Lucknow. The FAB mass spectrum of the complex was recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and the spectra were recorded at room temperature using *m*-nitrobenzylalcohol (NBA) as the matrix. The IR spectra of the samples were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer in 4000–200 cm^{-1} range using KBr pellet. The UV-Vis spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-1601 spectrophotometer using DMSO as solvent. The X-band ESR spectra of the complexes were recorded at 300 K and 77 K at IIT, Mumbai using TCNE (tetracyanoethylene) as the *g*-marker. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes were carried out by Guoy balance using copper sulphate as the calibrant. Electrochemical studies were carried out using EG & G Princeton Applied Research Potentiostat/Galvanostat Model 273A, controlled by M270 software. CV measurements were performed using a glassy carbon working electrode, platinum wire auxiliary electrode and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode. All solutions were purged with N_2 for 30 min prior to each set of experiments. The molar conductance of the complexes was measured using a Systronic conductivity bridge. Solutions of λ DNA in 50 mM tris-HCl/18 mM NaCl (pH = 7.0) gave a ratio of UV absorbance at 260 and 280 nm, A_{260}/A_{280} of ca. 1.8–1.9, indicating that the DNA was sufficiently free of protein contamination. The DNA concentration was determined by the UV absorbance at 260 nm after 1 : 100 dilutions. Stock solutions were kept at 4 °C and used after not more than 4 days. Doubly distilled H_2O was used to prepare the buffer.

Preparation of Schiff base : An ethanolic solution (50 mL) of *p*-aminoacetanilide (1.02 g, 5 mmol) and salicylaldehyde (2.03 g, 5 mmol) was boiled under reflux for 3 h. The solid that separated out at room temperature after 36 h was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in

desiccator over CaCl₂, m.p. 162 °C.

Preparation of metal complexes : The Schiff base (HL) (2.97 g, 10 mmol) dissolved in hot ethanol (50 mL) was added to a hot ethanolic solution (25 mL) of the metal salts (5 mmol). The pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted to 7–8 by the addition of aqueous ammonia. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2–3 h. The solid formed was filtered, washed with solvent and dried *in vacuo*. Yield : 52%.

References

1. N. J. Long, *Angew. Chem. Int. Engl.*, 1995, **34**, 21.
2. A. D. Garnovskii, A. L. Nivorozhkin and V. I. Minkin, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1993, **126**, 1.
3. E. N. Jacobsen, W. Zhang, A. R. Muci, J. R. Ecker and L. Deng, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **113**, 7063.
4. P. Espinet, M. A. Esteruelas, L. A. Oro, J. L. Serrano and E. Sola, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1992, **117**, 215.
5. S. Y. Zhou, W. L. Yan and C. Z. Guang, *Anal. Sci.*, 2004, **20**, 1127.
6. J. Liu, H. Zhang, C. Chen, H. Deng, T. Lu and L. Ji, *Dalton Trans.*, 2003, **119**, 114.
7. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
8. R. Ramesh and G. Venkatachalam, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 2285.
9. G. Venkatachalam, S. Maheswaran and R. Ramesh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 705.
10. R. Ramesh, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2004, **7**, 274.
11. S. N. Pal and S. Pal, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2002, 2102.
12. A. Chudhavy and R. V. Singh, *Indian. J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 2536.
13. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1977.
14. N. Raman, A. Kulandaisamy and C. Thangaraja, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2004, **29**, 129.
15. J. Lewis and R. G. Willkins, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1967.
16. L. Casella and M. Gullotti, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 6338.
17. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
18. K. Ramakrishna Reddy, K. Madhusudan Reddy and K. N. Mahendra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2006, **45**, 377.
19. M. L. Harikumar Nair, G. Mathew and M. R. Sudarsana Kumar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 85.
20. B. J. Hathaway and A. A. G. Tomlinson, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **5**, 1.
21. R. K. Ray and G. R. Kauffman, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1990, **173**, 207.
22. A. L. Sharma, I. O. Singh, M. A. Singh and H. R. Singh, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2001, **26**, 532.
23. J. Dolezal and K. Stulik, *J. Electroanal. Commun.*, 1986, **17**, 87.
24. M. Y. Abyanch and M. Fleischman, *J. Electroanal. Commun.*, 1961, **197**, 119.